

Artículos

From Humans That Move Like Machines to Machines That Move Like Humans:

A Multidisciplinary Review of the State of the Art in the Digitization of the Dancing Body

Jorge Poveda Yáñez

Rory Fewer

University of California, Riverside

> Abstract

The heightened circulation of digital renditions of dance and their reincorporation back into human bodies reveals a kind of permeability of cross-pollinating forces dialoguing fundamentally through gesture. The tensions, digressions, and reformulations of what movement means in the digital era have spawned discourses and innovations that need to be tackled through multiple disciplines, namely the computer sciences, the humanities, and the law, all of which have been considered for this study. First, we offer a review of what are currently the most prominent initiatives in the digital safeguarding of dance and movement globally, seen in tandem with the latest developments in the field of computerized movement recognition in the following section. We then examine the most salient criticisms from the humanities surrounding the digitization of human movement, which we follow with a compilation of relevant jurisprudence of conflicts dealing with the dancing body's merging with the digital. The purpose of this survey is to assist readers and practitioners in positioning their own projects related to the digitization of dance within a thriving field and suggest potential conceptual refigurations that such advances might produce to better grasp the leakages between humans and machines.

> Keywords

Dance, avatarization, digitization, intangible cultural heritage.

> Resumen

La creciente circulación de registros digitales de la danza – y la simulación del movimiento por vía computarizada- revelan la permeabilidad entre humanos y máquinas, como un dúo que se comunica kinéticamente. Las tensiones, conflictos y reformulaciones sobre lo que el movimiento implica para la era digital ha devenido en discursos e innovaciones que deben ser revisadas desde múltiples disciplinas incluyendo las ciencias computacionales, las humanidades y el derecho, todas las cuales hemos incluido en este estudio. Primero, ofrecemos una revisión rápida de las iniciativas actuales más destacadas en la preservación de la danza; vinculada con los avances en el campo de la captación de movimiento humano computarizado en la siguiente sección. Luego, las críticas más relevantes erigidas desde las humanidades sobre la migración del cuerpo danzante a lo digital son examinadas, seguidas de una compilación de las jurisprudencias relevantes que se han generado sobre la digitalización del cuerpo. La intención de este estudio diagnóstico es asistir a los/es/as lectores en el posicionamiento de sus propios estudios o iniciativas relativas a la digitalización de la danza, así como sugerir potenciales refiguraciones conceptuales que permitan entender mejor la migración de movimiento entre humanos y máquinas.

> Palabras claves

Danza, avatarización, digitalización, patrimonio cultural inmaterial.

IDyM Vol. 04, N° 08, Año 05. Abril 2023 – octubre 2023 [66-83]
*From Humans That Move Like Machines to Machines That Move Like
Humans* / Rory Fewer y Jorge Poveda Yáñez
ISSN 2683-9318

Artículos

From Humans That Move Like Machines to Machines That Move Like Humans:

A Multidisciplinary Review of the State of the Art in the Digitization of the Dancing Body

(...) the question of how to think movement imposes new points of view on the problem of the Idea and its recurrence throughout all the faculties of the mind. One of these viewpoints is movement as the object of a transcendental sensibility: movement as an idea that can only be sensed, a *sentiendum*, or a pure aesthetic object. Following Deleuze's system, we see how this *sentiendum* is also always connected to a *phantasteon* and a *memorandum*, or respectively what can only be imagined and what can only be remembered, movement as the object of imagination and memory in their most transcendental exercise

(Portanova, 2013: 7).

The reason why third-party CAPTCHA solver services and applications pay humans to solve CAPTCHA tests (Completely Automated Public Turing Test to Tell Computers and Humans Apart) is that computers have not successfully learned how to perfectly mimic the movements of a person. In an unexpected turn, what is ultimately deciding "who is a robot" or not within the digital, is movement. Regardless of whether one finds it coy or utterly cringeworthy to post videos of ourselves dancing on TikTok, movement still mediates the way in which we interact with machines. Oftentimes the data that is recorded from our online behavior is not limited to "either or" categories but is rather measured in trajectories. When we are presented with CAPTCHA puzzles to validate our humanness, it is not the ticking of correct boxes that is relevant to or read by machines but rather the actual movement pattern that our mouse cursor traces in the digital space while navigating from one box to the next (Dzieza, 2019).

Dance data, or dance turned into data, are perceivable in the form of images of people moving or representations of movement on screens and across devices, but they are not always exhausted by imitations or repetitions of the "real" dances that humans perform. As if these images were retaliating against us like simulations substituting the real (Baudrillard, 1994), digital representations of dance also spawn movements in real life. Human dancers convert dance data back into movement after viewing them on their devices, harboring them in their physical bodies. Countless dancers of flesh and bone are now replicating the way in which machines move, and not only the other way around. Replicating the dance steps that avatars perform in video games is an ascending trend on social media, evidenced by the wide viewership and circulation of this content. For instance, videos of dancers imitating the movements of a character from the video game *Fortnite* have earned as many as thirty-three million views on TikTok, while the hashtags #fortnitmoveschallenge and #fortnitmove have astonishingly high levels of engagement with over nine million views and one hundred eighteen million views, respectively. Similarly, TikTok user @gtamillionnata recently gained prominence for embodying an imitation of the now-iconic way in which

Artículos

characters in the video game series *Grand Theft Auto* move, amassing more than eighty million likes on one of her posts. These cross-pollinations between dance data and movement have not been produced within a vacuum but rather are the result of long and enduring lineages of cultural, technical, and aesthetic digressions that permit their close intertwining. For this reason, we deemed it beneficial to unpack the current state of the art in computer-mediated movement as an attempt to historicize the contingent conditions of the digitization of dance and hopefully offer the reader an overarching perspective of the advances, clashes, and limitations of the various fields that participate in it. Framed as a survey paper, this article offers a sampling of references to the works of choreographers, researchers, academics, courthouses, and computer scientists as a way to take the pulse on the consequences of dance as it makes its way into the digital.

First, we start with an illustrative review of current projects of movement digitization across cultures and practices. We then follow with an analysis of recent developments and experimentations carried out in the field of computer sciences to expand the tools for the digitization of the dancing body. The third section covers scholarship from the humanities that critically assesses the tangibilization of dance's ephemerality. The last two portions of this survey evaluate the concepts, tools, and constraints that legal jurisprudence in the United States has developed to shape the field in which the digitization of the moving body takes place. We hope that in addition to offering a snapshot of this historical conjuncture in the field, this text can also facilitate for readers and practitioners the assessment of what is possible in their practices, the limitations they might find in their own experimentations, as well as potential solutions to the mishaps they might encounter.

Introduction

The wave of dance digitization that started in 1990 (Huang & Dai, 2019) has reached a new summit due to the advancement of technological developments. Virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), cloud storage, the blockchain, artificial intelligence (AI), motion capture, and gamification are stretching the environment in which dance is preserved and practiced, from the stage to computerized landscapes (Alivizatou-Barakou et al., 2017). Museums and grassroots initiatives are likewise "going digital". Cultural heritage institutions have embraced the use of digital technologies to make items of cultural relevance accessible in interactive ways (Konach, 2018). Given the conversion of dance into data is a multidisciplinary effort encompassing computational power, the liveness of performance, and ethical considerations, we are therefore choosing not to parochialize our findings in any one field exclusively.

The pervasive circulation of movement turned into dance –and data that flows like movement– is becoming a staple of our era. The current "dance craze" of hundreds of millions of users on digital platforms, wherein infinite loops of codified gestures are shared (Marshall, 2019), is spreading in and out of the internet. Along with the joy of social media spaces that launch the stardom of dancing teenagers across the globe (Johnson, 2021), there are economic, social, authorial, artistic, and legal ramifications to spawning, copying, reproducing, and forwarding trendy dance moves (Vincent et al., 2018). In the following lines, we proceed to deploy the most salient references from recent years that approach the entangled issue of the digitization of the dancing body in relation to the safeguarding of dance. By providing a selection of examples from several different fields, we offer the following sections as a kaleidoscopic view of dance data's various instantiations before drawing larger conclusions from their interconnections.

Artículos

International heritage-driven initiatives of digital safeguarding

Like the battle tank that oscillates from museum displays to the war field and back (Steyerl, 2016), digitized versions of dance are stabilized samples of movement that refuse to remain in a historical past; they are ghosts that keep returning across time. The information contained in them – recorded through human movement technologies – is bound to re-impact dancers in the physical world, teaching later generations of movers how dance steps should be produced. There is a sustained expansion of initiatives aimed at using computer-assisted methods to record, process, and archive dance as a form of intangible cultural heritage (ICH). In Indonesia, for example, there are several efforts aimed at the digitization of embodied creativity for either animation-making purposes based on five traditional dances, Saman, Cokek, Yapong, Merak, and Incling (Hegarini et al., 2016), or to revive and flesh out the image of national heritage icons, such as Prince Diponegoro, in a digital way (Nuriman et al., 2021).

In the vein of efforts being carried out to safeguard dances that are considered ICH, Mustaffa and Zaffwan Idris (2017) employed motion capture and 3D modeling to record the Malay dance Zapin, one of the oldest traditions that fuses the Hadhramaut Arab dance with Malay performance styles. But they are not alone in benefiting from the possibilities that new human-movement recognition technologies can offer to the digitization and further documentation of embodied creativity in virtual repositories. Digital recording and preservation strategies are being applied to a diverse array of expressive practices, including: joget, a Malay folk dance (Mohd Herrow & Azraai, 2021); the corporeal and vocal training techniques of avant-garde theater group Odin Teatret in Denmark (Parente La Selva & Marouda, 2022); Cypriot folk dances as employed for emic educational purposes (Stavrakis et al., 2012); Thai sword dancing traditions in combination with gamification strategies (Kovavisaruch et al., 2011); the Lagzi dance from the Khorazm Region in Uzbekistan, inscribed as official ICH in 2019 (Skublewska-Paszkowska et al., 2021); and Maracatú ritual performances of the Umbanda-Jurema tradition from the State of Pernambuco in Brazil (Bonini Baraldi et al., 2021).

Another kind of technological coupling is seen in the work of Zhou and Mudur (2006), who paired the 3D scanning of faces with motion-capture registers of performers to offer a richly layered digital representation of Chinese opera repertoire. Martial arts choreographies have also been documented through state-of-the-art motion capture systems in Hong Kong, such as the Hong Kong Martial Arts Living Archive (HKMALA). As Chao et al. describe, the HKMALA “has captured over 120 sets of empty-hand and weapon sequences, known as ‘taolu’, representing nineteen martial art styles documented so far” (2018). It is relevant to note how these broader strategies for the digitization of ICH show a preference for recovering multi-modal data in symmetry to the different layers of the practice at stake, including information on costumes, 3D representations of tangible objects, immersive environments, video, audio, text, drawings, and other elements that collide to signal the richness of the cultural event. This is present in both the HKMALA and Chinese opera-related projects, but it figures even more prominently in geo-localized cultural heritage objects indexed through KIRA (Amato et al., 2017) and DECO’s (Aliaga et al., 2011) integrative model for multi-modal data of heritage-related objects with historical information.

Projects with such a holistic and interrelated stance towards the archiving of cultural heritage elements are made possible only through the interoperability of multilayered metadata schemes (Lourdi et al., 2007) and increasingly dynamic interfaces for information retrieval within exhibitions and collections (Whitelaw, 2015). Pointing in the direction of co-curatorial practices or community-based criteria for the categorization of ICH repositories, Hou et al. reflect on how traditional dances do not solely entail human movement but

Artículos

also involve “agents, locations, objects, in addition to rituals and traditional notes” (2022: 7). In a parallel impulse to visualize the patterns of dance in broader ways, choreographer William Forsythe digitized a selection of his dances using motion capture, which he then deployed through the now-paradigmatic website *Synchronous Objects for One Flat Thing, reproduced*. This website “was realized by using several mapping technologies; image processing, computer vision, 3D computer graphics, and interactive online algorithms were then deployed to explore the mapped data and to systematically formalize the components of the choreographic system” (Portanova, 2013: 85).

In addition to the digitization of the dancing body, including its likeness and dance steps, there is an emergent trend of practitioners “tokenizing” their creativity on blockchain architectures. Metamovers (Mayoral, n.d.) is a company that has tried to gain the attribution and stewardship of dance steps as they have started to circulate on the metaverse. Its projects include designing 2D representations of virtual characters performing dance moves that can later be used to mint unique NFTs on a blockchain, which are then ready to be sold to collectors and enthusiasts of crypto-art. Regardless of the type of dance being digitized, researchers and artists continue to sustain the “archive fever” that Derrida (1995) identified, now aligned with and reinvigorated by safeguarding discourses sprung from the UNESCO system and its 2003 Convention on Intangible Cultural Heritage. All of these protective efforts, however, are bound to the current constraints that digital technologies hold in practical terms. The ever-expanding possibilities of movement-recognition algorithms, the perfection of AI models for generative dance, and the enhancement of interoperable platforms for learning dance in the digital space continue to be the subject of research in the field of computer sciences and information technologies. Below we review salient projects from each of these lines of investigation to illustrate how the playground is being shaped by new and more encompassing devices for the digitization of embodied creativity.

Stretching the dance stage, one byte at a time

The misconception that digital technologies created for the abstraction of human movement are unprecedented developments is fostered by the ostentatious displays of the human body that they are capable of rendering, represented with varying degrees of evisceration of its organic interiority. Following Gilroy, Cherniavsky frames this increasing pervasiveness of human fleshiness as “the transition from peering technologies (that look into the body) to screening technologies (that turn the body inside out, a quantity of information manipulated on a computer screen)” (2006: xxi). To be clear, the mapping of the dancing body through abstraction and its conversion into numerical order dates back to fifteenth-century Italian and French dance masters and their treaties (see Bench, 2016; Leigh Foster, 2010). In “Body: Notation, Reconstruction, and Reinvention in Dance”, Franko (2011) interweaves a history of notation techniques and documentation strategies for dance, including the notation of coded steps in humanistic treaties of the Renaissance era, non-word tracking systems, still images portraying the body and its itinerary in space, and the development of modern notation techniques. As such, the tangibilization of dance is more of an enduring tradition than an unprecedented effort.

While today we might have video recordings, photography, Labanotation, and motion capture, the Italian masters of the Renaissance era had already established notational techniques combining “text, tablatures, and illustrations of attitudes” (Norman, 2016: 244), such as the notations of Fabritio Caroso “Il Ballarino”, published in Venice in 1581. These are different tools enabled by vastly different technological affordances

Artículos

but centered around the same intention. Current iterations of this impulse to tangibilize dance include: the production of automatic Labanotated scores from hidden Markov models (Li et al., 2017); the customization of users' "virtual selves" while dancing (El Raheb, 2018); the facilitation of whole-body interaction learning experiences of dance (Camurri et al., 2016); the training of AI models to produce their own dance movements (Wallace et al., 2021); and the usage of motion capture data to quantitatively identify how genre-specific music can alter dance production (Carlson et al., 2020).

More recently, applications programmed to retrieve motion capture data from regular video input are paving the way for broader developments and research, as well as commercial and safeguarding initiatives. OpenPose (Cao et al., 2017) is a system that employs machine learning to identify human poses directly from video footage in real-time. This prototype, available online, renders positional information in 2D. While it might not be as accurate as state-of-the-art motion capture laboratories based on infrared cameras, such as those that utilize Qualisys, it holds great possibilities for grassroots organizations that are interested in digitally documenting dance as a way of preserving ICH but are unable to purchase thousands of dollars' worth of specialized equipment. One example of this is Embodying Reconciliation, a Colombia-based nonprofit organization that has invested in a system to revitalize folkloric dances through the creation of a project called the *Bodies for Empathy Museum*. This project, developed in 2020 and endorsed by the Mayor's Office of the City of Bogotá, entails a motion capture platform that is available from any web browser and only requires a device with a camera and an internet connection. This initiative offers practitioners of both folk and contemporary dance forms across Colombia a new medium for the tangibilization of their dances (Poveda Yáñez & Davies, 2021: 16).

In the case of information retrieval, the quest for fast, content-based indexing of motion clips imposes the need for high-level traits of the dancing body, such as Boolean features of geometric relations between body segments. Regarding machine learning methods, on the other hand, there has been a recent increase in initiatives oriented toward motion recognition and generation. Holden et al. (2016) used convolutional autoencoders to synthesize the movement of an animated character along trajectories altered by the user. Abidine et al. (2018) performed more efficient human activity recognition (HAR) using weighted support vector machines, and Hassan et al. (2018) performed HAR using deep neural networks trained on wearable body sensors' data. Although trained machine learning models can be relatively compact and are often inexpensive at run-time, training the models often requires large amounts of data and processing power. Using them for clustering or classifying movement also requires labeled data, which can create challenges as there are currently a limited number of labeled datasets for dance moves.

Finally, beyond information retrieval and processing, the different ways in which data recorded from human bodies is represented can be rendered in more visual ways, enhancing researchers' ability to leverage and share their own dance data. Stemming from musicological studies, Jensenius' (2018) "video-visualization techniques" have been designed to gain greater insight into what might appear to be "just movement" or plain data. These techniques take the form of software that portrays bodily activity according to different time frames, foregrounding salient traits of how people perform movement in space and time. It produces "motion history images", which are diagrams made to visualize movement trajectories over short periods of time, as well as "motion average images", which summarize the spatial distribution of entire sequences of movement all at once (i.e. the recurrent trajectories that the body can trace excluding their temporal differentiation). "Motiongrams", on the other hand, display the spatiotemporal development of longer movement sequences, allowing for the broad visualization of an important portion of data based on how the body moves across space. The acquisition, analysis, visualization, and further re-utilization of

Artículos

motion capture data, including those gathered via these “video-visualization techniques”, proves to be a fruitful endeavor for numerous applications, though it is not without tensions and criticisms. While the fields of computer sciences and information technologies continue to enthusiastically expand the algorithms responsible for the detection and classification of human movement, perspectives from the humanities and the arts problematize its conversion into data with greater suspicion, as will be described below.

Digressions on the ephemerality of the dancing body

The resulting data from the digitization of dance that can be extrapolated to various virtual bodies or avatars is considered a valuable asset. However, if they are to be conceptualized more poetically as in the case of Kim (2019), this data can also be understood as a transcorporeal “ghost” that populates both bodies and devices alike. This metaphoric definition of motion capture data foregrounds its ductile nature, especially if we consider how its infinite reproducibility across bodies (virtual or physical) spreads. And even though a “ghost” might invoke ideas of abstraction and blurriness, the opposite holds true for the unprecedented specificity with which motion capture records the dancing body. This imperishable viscosity has brought Barber (2015) and Warren-Crow (2017) to reflect on how racial markers are still palpable in such motion capture data, even when performed by animalistic, robotic, or anthropomorphic 3D-modeled avatars across the digital space. Davies (2022) describes how the migration of motion capture data across bodies is far from being confined within the digital space, as it keeps being reintroduced back to the “real world” through artistic or even entrepreneurial efforts. Following this premise, the movements underlying viral sensations and 3D-modeled images of bodies dancing across the internet can be understood to affect how human bodies perform a dance in the “real world”, as recovered over the examples in the introduction section. This constant permeation of the “real” and the “digital” worlds that influence and inform how people move and dance, both in and out of digital spaces, is part of a continuum that is only now starting to be identified.

According to Kozel, “to deny the abstract qualities of the real (...) body, like denying the sensuous qualities of a virtual creation, is to ghettoize both the real and the virtual in definitional constructs that are incomplete” (2008: 236). In fact, Bergs (2022) and Davies (2020) critically connect the highly-detailed ways in which the dancing body is digitized by motion capture, precisely as the enabler for its further commodification. Similarly, the artwork *Factory of the Sun* (Steyerl, 2015) tells a fantastic story of workers whose involuntary dance steps in a motion capture facility are turned into artificial sunshine. Such a speculative narrative, however, actually describes the astonishing reality of contemporary video game companies and the massive revenues they generate from selling motion capture data from uncredited dancers. Companies like Epic Games collect around three hundred million dollars per month from selling the motion capture data of people dancing trendy steps to video game players (Kain, 2018). Accurately described by Ravetto-Biagioli (2021), this digitization of the dancing body spawns a “data body” that renders it difficult to know who plays and who is being played, at least in the context of the intricate dynamics of immersive video games like *Just Dance* or *Dance Central*, wherein dance data and its automatic transmission gives place to the commodification of images of oneself dancing pre-defined kinetic scripts.

Current initiatives aimed at digitizing the dancing body draw on innovative technological developments to record, visualize, and reproduce it, but they are also instrumentalized within an overarching and ongoing project of archivalization. Even though different theoretical frameworks regarding embodied archives or

Artículos

repositories (Lepecki, 2010; Taylor, 2003) have been created, most digitization projects reiterate the “phase of patrimonialization” that Santova (2018) identified in the overarching agenda of dance’s safeguarding, as if dealing with any other kind of material. According to Santova, items of cultural value continue to migrate into repositories and archives, a phenomenon marked by the establishment of new managerial and bureaucratic hierarchies that become not only politically driven but also technologically fueled. As dance practices make their entrance into the regime of the digital, whose technocratic stewards propel culture as data, new selection processes are at play when dances and bodies from the stage are preserved into virtuality (or not). Such processes have led in the past to controversies that illustrate the convoluted and cross-pollinating enmeshment of digital technological developments, live performance, and the law. These conflicts have usually sprung legal tensions that we review in more detail over the following section in the hope of offering readers and practitioners a comprehensive view of the field of the digitization of dance.

Latest considerations from the field of law

Following many debates within the humanities and the arts surrounding the ephemerality of dance (Charmatz 2014; Fischer-Lichte 2008; Phelan 2003; Pritchard & Mawdsley 2010; Taylor 2003) and the impossibility of digital technology – or any technology for that matter – to fully capture the “ontology of live performance” (Phelan, 2003), the discussion on the digitization of the performing arts has taken an important turn. As Bench accurately puts it:

Nor could performance scholars have foreseen that the most pronounced tensions would not concern a philosophical contention between performance and documentation, but a legal debate between access and circulation on the one hand and monetization and copyright/intellectual property on the other (2016: 157).

The proliferation of artistic creations in dance that are homage-based or spin-offs is described by Vincent et al. (2018) as a result of new, widely available information technologies that facilitate the cross-platform appropriation of dance. Others, such as Waelde et al. (2014), remark on how the exploitation of dance may give rise to new business models for the performing arts, which, no longer bounded to royalty streams from the licensing of recorded forms of dance, can instead leverage the circulation of dance on social media and other digital platforms as it is fixed in other forms, such as computer animation or motion capture data. In addition, Ravetto-Biagioli (2020) points out how these new iterations of dance in the digital space involve other potential property holders (in addition to the choreographer or dancer), such as videographers, computer engineers, and software designers behind the datafication of movement. There is, however, an important legal distinction to be made between trying to own a contemporary dance versus a traditional dance. Legal scholar Charlotte Waelde highlights how every contemporary dance is in principle protectable through copyright, but when it comes to dances that belong to the ICH of a community there are different legal provisions:

A traditional dance, such as a waltz or a tango that is recorded on a film, will be protected only in relation to the particular rendition of the dance. In other words, the owner of the copyright in the film could prevent third parties copying the film without permission, but other dancers – whether amateur or professional – could not be prevented from dancing a waltz, or dancing a tango (Waelde, 2018: 329).

Artículos

Ravetto-Biagioli (2021) describes subjectivity, personhood, and the self as prerequisites to owning choreography, or any other type of property, while underpinning how the internet and large businesses like YouTube and Google not only refrain from guaranteeing the stewardship of cultural heritage products to their original communities but are also ready to alienate and commodify the personhood and identity of its members, thus removing the basis upon which the claim to property of any kind rests. These conflicts and tensions surrounding the dancing body's entrance into the digital have not been exclusively theoretical either; on the contrary, they have escalated to the courtroom. Following the multidisciplinary spirit of this survey, we foreground those cases and jurisprudence below to offer the reader further insight into how future conflicts might be navigated.

Jurisprudence and related legal feuds

The ownership of dance material sits at a crossroads of legal, aesthetic, technological, and social considerations, which in the words of scholar Anthea Kraut is evidence of the clash between “dancing economies” (2016: 276). To maintain a sense of agency and gain protection for their creative productions, dancers have been forced to become just as innovative with their navigation of legal processes as they are with their choreography making. Kraut recounts the high-profile case of dancer Loie Fuller, who “turned to patent law to protect the stage devices she used in her productions” (2011: 19) after confronting the impossibility of protecting her abstract dances at a time when the granting of legal protection was largely based on the plot of a work:

On April 8, 1893, Fuller secured a French patent on a “garment for dancers” – a skirt and bodice with wands attached to the skirt that enabled the dancer to manipulate the material. So began a string of patents that Fuller obtained, not only in France but in the United States and Germany as well, on effects such as a mirrored room and a mechanism that illuminated a dancer's figure from below the stage (Harris, 1979 in Kraut, 2011: 19).

In 1952, choreographers like Hanya Holm circumvented the exclusion of dance as a copyrightable creation by registering their pieces as “dramatico-musical compositions” (Kraut, 2010: 165) due to the availability of Labanotation as a new method of rendering tangible the choreographic materials that had previously been transmitted orally within minoritized communities. In Australia, Indigenous communities have used contract law to expand the individualistic approach of intellectual property regimes as a means of obtaining collective ownership of their traditional dances, even when re-framed for the stage. For example, Bangarra Dance Theatre developed its own legal model through a private letter of agreement with representatives of the Mnyarrun Clan (Rimmer, 2000: 278) to establish the sharing of profits and authorship of their dances. Other companies, such as Oedo Sukeroku Taiko in Japan, have exercised pragmatic vigilance over the reproduction of their works by verbally warning practitioners and third parties to not perform the sequences and movements of their original repertoire without authorization (González, 2020: 37). This peer-to-peer monitoring was previously identified as a practice within the community of African American tap and jazz dancers in the mid-twentieth century, deployed in the form of “vigilant surveillance and public castigation in response to perceived theft in commercial settings” (Kraut, 2010: 182). In other instances, the difficulty of protecting one's dance has pushed practitioners to follow Fuller's unorthodox approach by obtaining patents not for the movements in themselves but for the technical

Artículos

equipment necessary for their execution. Oedo Sukeroku Taiko used this strategy when it patented its slant stand for its percussion instruments (González, 2020) as a way to distinguish themselves from imitators and establish a sense of authenticity. Other more recent initiatives have created formal crediting conventions to express sharing protocols that do not traditionally fall within the scope of legal protection. For example, Embodying Reconciliation, a Colombian nonprofit organization, has employed Traditional Knowledge Labels developed by Local Contexts to encourage proper governance and attribution of traditional dances in Colombia (Poveda Yáñez & Davies, 2021: 15).

If the clash of dance economies implies a set of contradicting interests, it likewise involves various stakeholders and the power relations between them. Authorities and policymakers make decisions that shape the playground in which dance communities can establish relationships with both their own works and other practitioners. In this sense, it is relevant to review the aspects that courtrooms have taken into consideration when making decisions regarding the illegitimate reproduction of one's movements and likeness via virtual avatars. These decisions have impacted the economic and legal aspirations of plaintiffs and defendants alike, but more crucially, they have generated a rich jurisprudence with conceptually informed angles that, in turn, outline the expectations for the rights of contemporary practitioners when commodifying their works in the digital sphere or contesting such processes. As image rights, privacy rights, likeness-related rights, and free speech protections are pondered, the digitization of an individual's personhood is further foregrounded, adding to the discussion of its integrity when migrating between analog and digital milieus.

In the case *Keller v. Electronic Arts, Inc.*, the protection granted to the video game company Electronic Arts by the First Amendment was deemed insufficient to justify the inclusion of the likeness of a student-athlete (Keller) in the form of a digital avatar playing football in one of its sports video games. The rationale behind this decision is that the student athlete was included in the software performing movements and gestures precisely related to that which made him famous in the first place, playing college football. A similar case, *Hart v. Electronic Arts, Inc.*, had an opposing resolution on First Amendment grounds given that the video game which included the likeness of another student athlete (Hart) allowed for users to customize their avatars altering the appearance of the real-life people they were modeled after. This crucial element allowed for protection under the First Amendment since Electronic Arts could argue that its product was transformative enough, or in other words, that it departed from reality in a way that was creative enough to constitute "an expression on its own".¹ In the case *No Doubt v. Activision Publishing, Inc.*, the prominent band *No Doubt* sued the software company Activision for including the likeness of its members in the video game *Band Hero*. The avatars available in the video game were considered to exhaust Activision's First Amendment protection because they were an exact reference to the band members and were seen doing movements identical to those which they are known for doing, namely performing on a stage. Following this rationale, the software was not considered to be transformative enough and was therefore unable to claim free speech rights in this case.² These first three cases reviewed were solved by pondering the degree of creative work of the disputed materials and whether or not they could be protected by the free speech rights of their creators, but there are other cases regarding the digital reproduction of the likeness of artists that have been discussed on the grounds of preventing consumers' confusion instead.

Ginger Rogers, a dancer who found herself watching a movie portraying an artist performing her choreography, was unsuccessful in disputing the reproduction of her identity and work given that the third

¹ NCAA Student-Athlete Name Likeness Licensing Litig., 724 F.3d 1268, 1271 (9th Cir. 2013), *Keller v Elec. Arts, Inc.*,

² *No Doubt v. Activision Publ'g Inc.*, 192 Cal. App. 4th 1018, 1022-24 (2011)

Artículos

party's product was not using Rogers' name to deceive people into buying a product unrelated to it.³ *Rogers v. Grimaldi* is a prime example of jurisprudence spawning a technical tool that, while first intended for use in the case at hand, is used *a posteriori* when similar conflicts arise to identify when it is legitimate to reproduce and circulate the presence of a real person and their movements in a third party's material.

For cases involving the digitization of a performer's identity, three tests are widely used to assess whether the new material infringes on publicity rights or should be granted protection as an exercise of free speech in the United States (Le, 2020). The first test is the *Rogers* test, which evaluates whether an artistic work confuses consumers and is therefore not afforded First Amendment protection based on it satisfying two requirements: the title of the artistic work must not have relevance to the content of the work itself, and the title must explicitly mislead as to the source or content of the work. This approach is limited, however, as there exist works that copy the likeness of performers without necessarily deceiving consumers by using irrelevant or misleading titles. The second test is the "predominant use test" (based on *Doe v. TCI Cablevision*), which determines if a work is not afforded First Amendment protection based on it primarily exploiting the commercial value of another person's identity. In these cases, commercial exploitation is considered to exceed the creative intent behind the expressive work. The third test is the "transformative use test", which evaluates if a work is not afforded First Amendment protection based on it failing to sufficiently transform the likeness of an original character. In these cases, the appropriation of likeness is not considered to be transformative enough to substantiate an expression "on its own".⁴

Closure

The above survey encompasses the current state of the art in the digitization of the dancing body, illustrated through examples of safeguarding projects, computerized developments, and artistic discourses that interact throughout the capture, visualization, and reproduction of dance practices in the digital. As seen, the efforts to archive dance practices develop reciprocally in close isometry with the pragmatic affordances made available by technical advances in the field of computer sciences. The latter, based on the literature revised, constantly springs an array of new technical features fueled conspicuously by the desire to advance previous software or devices in the field of automated human movement recognition. Complementarily, these ever-evolving developments seem to be more often than not received with suspicion, particularly within the arenas of the humanities and performance studies, fields with a clear investment in the phenomenon of non-mediated live human presence. The intersections between these two fields, in turn, have inaugurated unprecedented conflicts that are directly correlated to the accelerated circulation of kinetic material across digital spaces. Stemming from these controversies of the digital age, the legal field is compelled to feed back into this discussion notions, tests, and jurisprudence that we have compiled here not necessarily for their enforcing value but rather as positioned discourses with conceptually charged decisions relevant to the field. Given that all of the cases reviewed correspond to U.S. courts, these developments can only regain significance for the American reader if understood as potential resources to expand the current ideas of corporeality, self-possessive individualism, and the commodification of the

³ *Rogers v. Grimaldi*, 875 F.2d 994, 996-97 (2d Cir. 1989)

⁴ *Campbell v. Acuff-Rose Music, Inc.*, 510 U.S. 569, 579 (1994)

Artículos

human presence in the digital.

After finalizing a movement sequence, choreographers need effective methods of transmitting the dance to their apprentices. In a parallel situation, once motion capture files are generated, they are ready to be exported and reproduced by the divergent anatomies of virtually infinite avatars. In the second scenario, there is no didactic element but rather the limitless reproduction of numeric information. Digital avatars, regardless of looking like a squirrel, an alien, or a robot, reproduce the sequences of movement contained in a motion capture file. This reproducibility of markers moving along X, Y, and Z axes enacts and triggers various other consequences, whose refiguring of previous understandings of the pedagogy of dance and cultural transmission remains pending. Examples of this would include research informed by neurosciences that can shed new light on the cognitive transformations of consuming and reproducing dance both on and off the screen, as well as renewed frameworks around embodied archives and corporeal knowledges in their interactions with and across the digital.

We foresee an identifiable trend of dance's increasing value based on its translatability to flows of information or data; that is, its potential to be translated into texts that are better suited to be read by machines rather than by other humans. But beyond the political or institutional censures that such a stance could unleash, we suggest that the current environment of constant contaminations between humans and machines sharing movements needs to be studied from an expansive perspective that spreads past two common ideas: the reification of the known boundaries that parochialize the human presence and the virtual in mutually repelling fields, and the intent to theorize their interconnections from an exclusively catastrophizing stance that overinflates the angst for the replaceability of the latter by the former.

We enthusiastically await future projects of theorization and practical artistic applications to reconsider the necessity of unpacking and disentangling the phenomena of dance traveling on and off the screen through previously disregarded outlooks. To that effect, we gesture towards a renewed interest in gauging the specific patterns that dance traces as it is transformed into data, stretching beyond the utilitarianism of deploying dance as flows of machine-readable information in an information society, to disentangle what morphs and what is left behind as bodies become bytes. As such, we offer a final provocation to ask ourselves, what else is possible in this *pas de deux* between humans and machines, beyond the "archive fever" of safeguarding the maximum amount of practices from oblivion? What else can be said about "movement" as a cross-media phenomenon with the potential of tinting bodies and devices alike?

> Referencias

Abidine, Bilal M'hamed, Fergani, Lamy, Fergani, Belkacem, Oussalah, Mourad. (2018). The joint use of sequence features combination and modified weighted SVM for improving daily activity recognition. *Pattern Analysis and Applications*, 21, 119-138. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10044-016-0570-y>.

Aliaga, Daniel G., Bertino, Elisa, Valtolina, Stefano. (2011). DECHO—a framework for the digital exploration of cultural heritage objects. *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage*, 3(3), 1-26. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1145/1921614.1921619>.

Alivizatou-Barakou, Marilena et al. (2017). Intangible cultural heritage and new technologies: Challenges

Artículos

- and opportunities for cultural preservation and development in Ioannides, Marinos, Magnenat-Thalmann, Nadia, Papagiannakis, George (eds.). *Mixed Reality and Gamification for Cultural Heritage* (pp. 129-158). Cham: Springer.
- Amato, Flora, Moscato, Vincenzo, Picariello, Antonio, Sperlí, Giancarlo. (2017). KIRA: A system for knowledge-based access to multimedia art collections. *2017 IEEE 11th International Conference on Semantic Computing (ICSC)*, 338-343. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSC.2017.59>.
- Barber, Tiffany E. (2015). *Ghostcatching and After Ghostcatching*, dances in the dark. *Dance Research Journal*, 47(1), 44-67. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0149767715000030>.
- Baudrillard, Jean. (1994) [1981]. *Simulacra and simulation* (Sheila F. Glaser, trans). Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Bench, Harmony. (2016). Dancing in digital archives: Circulation, pedagogy, performance in Maikke Bleeker (ed.). *Transmission in Motion* (pp. 155-167). New York: Routledge.
- Bergs, Steyn. (2022). *Control copy: Digital reproducibility and the valorization of contemporary art* [PhD thesis – Research and graduation internal] Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. VU Campus Portal. Retrieved from <https://research.vu.nl/en/publications/control-copy-digital-reproducibility-and-the-valorization-of-cont>.
- Bonini Baraldi, Filippo, Davies, Matthew E. P., Viana, André, Térico, Daniel. (2021). Multi-modal recordings of Maracatu de Baque Solto (Brazil): Technical concerns and preliminary analyses in Polak, Rainer, Repetto, Rafael Caro, Holzapfel, Andre, Pearson, Lara (eds.). *Proceedings of the First Symposium of the ICTM Study Group on Sound, Movement, and the Sciences (SoMoS)* (pp. 11-15). Stockholm: KTH Royal Institute of Technology.
- Cao, Zhe, Simon, Tomas, Wei Shi-En, Sheikh, Yaser. (2017). Realtime multi-person 2D pose estimation using Part Affinity Fields. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 7291-7299. Computer Vision Foundation.
- Camurri, Antonio, El Raheb, Katerina, Even-Zohar, Oshri, Ioannidis, Yannis, Markatzi, Amalia, Matos, Jean-Marc, Morley-Fletcher, Edwin, Palacio, Pablo, Romero, Muriel, Sarti, Augusto, Di Pietro, Stefano, Viro, Vladimir, Whatley, Sarah. (2016). "WhoLoDancE: Towards a methodology for selecting Motion Capture Data across different Dance Learning Practices". *MOCO '16: Proceedings of the 3rd International Symposium on Movement and Computing* (1-2). New York: Association for Computing Machinery.
- Carlson, Emily, Saari, Pasi, Burger Birgitta, Toiviainen, Petri. (2020). Dance to your own drum: Identification of musical genre and individual dancer from motion capture using machine learning. *Journal of New Music Research*, 49 (2), 162-177. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2020.1711778>.
- Chao, Hing, Delbridge, Matt, Kenderdine, Sarah, Nicholson, Lydia, Shaw, Jeffrey. (2018). Kapturing Kung Fu: Future proofing the Hong Kong Martial Arts Living Archive in Whatley, Sarah, Cisneros, Rosamaria K., Sabiescu, Amalia (eds.). *Digital Echoes: Spaces for Intangible and Performance-based Cultural Heritage* (pp. 249-264). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Charmatz, Boris. (2014). Interview with Boris Charmatz. *Dance Research Journal*, 46(3), 49-52. Retrieved

Artículos

- from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43966141>.
- Cherniavsky, Eva. (2006). *Incorporations: Race, nation, and the body politics of capital*. Minneapolis: Univeristy of Minnesota Press.
- Davies, Nina. (2020). *Express yourself in the battlefield*. London: Emergency Festival, Performing the Pandemics.
- Davies, Nina. (2022). *Bionic step*. London: Overmorrow House.
- Derrida, Jacques, Prenowitz, Eric. (1995). Archive fever: A Freudian impression. *Diacritics*, 25(2), 9-63. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.2307/465144>.
- Dzieza, Josh. (2019, February 1). Why CAPTCHAs have gotten so difficult. *The Verge*. Retrieved from <https://www.theverge.com/2019/2/1/18205610/google-captcha-ai-robot-human-difficult-artificial-intelligence>.
- El Raheb, Katerina, Tsampounaris, George, Katifori, Akrivi, Ioannidis, Yannis. (2018). Choreomorphy: A whole-body interaction experience for dance improvisation and visual experimentation. *AVI '18: Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces*, (27), 1-9. New York: Association for Computing Machinery.
- Fischer-Lichte, Erika. (2008). *The transformative power of performance: A new aesthetics* (Saskya Iris Jain, trans.). London: Routledge.
- Franko, Mark. (2011). Writing for the body: Notation, reconstruction, and reinvention in dance. *Common Knowledge*, 17(2), 321-334. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1215/0961754x-1188004>.
- González, Paola. (2020). *Tradition and innovation: Embodiment of transmission practices of a professional taiko group in Japan* [Graduate thesis]. Norwegian University of Science and Technology].
- Hassan, Mohammad Mehedi, Huda, Shamsul, Uddin, Md Zia, Almogren, Ahmad, Alrubaiyan, Majed. (2018). Human activity recognition from body sensor data using deep learning. *Journal of Medical Systems*, 42(6), 99. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-018-0948-z>.
- Hegarini, Ega, Dharmayanti, Syakur, Abdus. (2016). Indonesian tradition dance motion capture documentation. *2016 2nd International Conference on Science and Technology-Computer (ICST)*, 108-111. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers.
- Holden, Daniel, Saito, Jun, Komura, Taku. (2016). A deep learning framework for character motion synthesis and editing. *ACM Transactions on Graphics*, 35(4), 1-11. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1145/2897824.2925975>.
- Hou, Yumeng, Kenderdine, Sarah, Picca, Davide, Egloff, Mattia, Adamou, Alessandro. (2022). Digitizing intangible cultural heritage embodied: State of the art. *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage*, 15(3), 1-20. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1145/3494837>.
- Huang, Wann, Dai, Fei. (2019). Research on digital protection of Intangible Cultural Heritage based on

Artículos

- blockchain technology. *Information Management and Computer Science*, 2(2), 14-18. Retrieved from <http://doi.org/10.26480/imcs.02.2019.14.18>.
- Jensenius, Alexander Refsum. (2018). Methods for studying music-related body motion in Bader, Rolf (ed.). *Springer Handbook of Systematic Musicology* (pp. 802-818). Berlin: Springer.
- Johnson, Ali. (2021). Copyrighting TikTok dances: Choreography in the internet age. *Washington Law Review*, 96(3), 1225. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.law.uw.edu/wlr/vol96/iss3/12>.
- Kain, Erik. (2018, Jun 26). 'Fortnite' made over \$300 million in May as 'Pokémon Go' surges. *Forbes*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/erikkain/2018/06/26/fortnite-made-over-300-million-pokemon-go-still-going-strong/?sh=7a57e20d34fa>.
- Kim, Eugenia S. (2019). Ghost in the virtual reality: Translating the human essence with motion captured dance. *Proceedings of EVA London 2019*, 250-255. BCS Learning and Development.
- Konach, Teodora. (2018). Presenting the intangible: Curating the intangible cultural heritage in the museum practice—legal aspects in Whatley, Sarah, Cisneros, Rosamaria K., Sabiescu, Amalia (eds.). *Digital Echoes: Spaces for Intangible and Performance-based Cultural Heritage* (pp. 267-281). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Kovavisaruch, La-or, Wisanmongkol, Juthatip, Sanpachuda, T., Chaiwongyen, A., Wisadsud, S., Wongsatho, T., Tangkamcharoen, B., Nagarachinda, B., Khiawchaum, C. (2011). Conserving and promoting Thai sword dancing traditions with Motion Capture and the Nintendo Wii. *2011 Proceedings of PICMET'11: Technology Management in the Energy Smart World (PICMET)*, 1-5. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers.
- Kozel, Susan. (2008). *Closer: Performance, technologies, phenomenology*. Cambridge: The MIT Press.
- Kraut, Anthea. (2010). 'Stealing steps' and signature moves: Embodied theories of dance as intellectual property. *Theatre Journal*, 62(2), 173-89. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1353/tj.0.0357>.
- Kraut, Anthea. (2011). White womanhood, property rights, and the campaign for choreographic copyright: Loïe Fuller's 'Serpentine Dance'. *Dance Research Journal*, 43(1), 2-26. Retrieved from <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/446663>.
- Kraut, Anthea. (2016). *Choreographing copyright: Race, gender and intellectual property rights in American dance*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Le, Nam. (2021). Trademark law—Looking out for the big guys: Outdated precedent reveals the need for new legal test in Fortnite likeness case—Pellegrino v. Epic Games, Inc., 451 F. Supp. 3d 373 (E.D. Pa. 2020). *Suffolk Journal of Trial and Appellate Advocacy*, 26(2). Retrieved from <https://dc.suffolk.edu/jtaa-suffolk/vol26/iss2/12>.
- Leigh Foster, Susan. (2010). *Choreographing empathy. Kinesthesia in performance*. London: Routledge.
- Lepecki, André. (2010). The body as archive: Will to re-enact and the afterlives of dances. *Dance Research*

Artículos

- Journal*, 42(2), 28-48. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0149767700001029>.
- Li, Min, Miao, Zhenjiang, Ma, Cong. (2017). Automatic Labanotation generation from motion-captured data based on Hidden Markov Models. *2017 4th IAPR Asian Conference on Pattern Recognition (ACPR)*, 793-798. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers.
- Lourdi, Irene, Papatheodorou, Christos, Nikolaidou, Mara. (2007). A multi-layered metadata schema for digital folklore collections. *Journal of Information Science*, 33(2), 197-213. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551506070711>.
- Marshall, Wayne. (2019). Social dance in the age of (anti-)social media: Fortnite, online video, and the jook at a virtual crossroads. *Journal of Popular Music Studies*, 31(4), 3-15. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1525/jpms.2019.31.4.3>.
- Mayoral, Dylan. (n.d.) The future of dance. *Metamovers*. Retrieved July 12, 2020 from <https://www.metamovers.io>.
- Mohd Herrow, Mohd Firdaus, Azraai, Nur Zaidi. (2021). Digital preservation of intangible cultural heritage of joget dance movement using motion capture technology. *International Journal of Heritage Art and Multimedia*, 4(15), 1-13. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.35631/IJHAM.415001>.
- Mustaffa, Norsimaa, Zaffwan Idris, Muhammad. (2017). Accessing accuracy of structural performance on basic steps in recording Malay Zapin dance movement using Motion Capture. *Journal of Applied Environmental and Biological Sciences*, 7(11), 165-173. Retrieved from [https://www.textroad.com/pdf/JAEBS/J.%20Appl.%20Environ.%20Biol.%20Sci.,%207\(11\)165-173,%202017.pdf](https://www.textroad.com/pdf/JAEBS/J.%20Appl.%20Environ.%20Biol.%20Sci.,%207(11)165-173,%202017.pdf).
- Norman, Sally Jane. (2016). Between grammatization and live movement sampling in Maikke Bleeker (ed.). *Transmission in Motion*, (pp. 185-198). London: Routledge.
- Nuriman, Harry, Sabana, Setiawan, Mutiaz, Intan Rizky, Andryanto, Rikrik Kusmara. (2021). Gesture visualization from Babad Diponegoro (UNESCO's MoW) into digital character using motion capture. *International Journal of Science and Society*, 3(2), 113-121. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.54783/ijssoc.v3i2.322>.
- Parente La Selva, Adriana, Marouda, Ioulia. (2022). "Practicing Odin Teatret's archives: Virtual translations of embodied knowledge through archival practices". *ISEA2022 Barcelona, International Symposium on Electronic Art, Proceedings*, 1160-1165. Barcelona: Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, ISEA International.
- Phelan, Peggy. (2003). *Unmarked: The politics of performance*. New York: Routledge.
- Pritchard, Helen, Mawdsley, Caroline. (2010). *The Pigs of Today are the Hams of Tomorrow*. Plymouth Arts Centre, Plymouth, United Kingdom.
- Portanova, Stamatia. (2013). *Moving without a body: Digital philosophy and choreographic thoughts*. Cambridge: The MIT Press.

Artículos

- Poveda Yáñez, Jorge, Wallace, Benedikte. (2021). Using motion capture technologies to assess the degree of similarity for intangible cultural heritage expressions. *International Online Conference on Digital Transformation in Culture and Education, 1st, Abstracts*. Online (Serbia).
- Poveda Yáñez, Jorge, Wallace, Benedikte. (2021). Dancing someone else's movements through someone else's body: The process of commodification of the digital dancing body and the arising tensions with intellectual property regimes. *Dance Articulated*, 7(1), 5-22. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5324/da.v7i1.4224>.
- Ravetto-Biagioli, Kriss. (2020). Whose dance is it anyway?: Property, copyright, and the commons. *Theory, Culture & Society*, 38(1), 101-126. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276420925534>.
- Ravetto-Biagioli, Kriss. (2021). Dancing with and within the digital domain. *Body & Society*, 27(2), 3-31. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/1357034X20979033>.
- Rimmer, Matthew. (2000). Bangarra Dance Theatre: Copyright law and Indigenous culture. *Griffith Law Review*, 9(2), 274-302. Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=600824>.
- Santova, Mila. (2015). Development of national inventories and cultural policies: The Bulgarian perspective. *The IOV Journal of Intangible Cultural Heritage*, 1, 34-49.
- Stavrakis, Efstathios, Aristidou, Andreas, Savva, Maria, Himona, Stephania Loizidou, Chrysanthou Yiorgos. (2012). Digitization of Cypriot folk dances in Ioannides, Marinou, Fritsch, Dieter, Leissner, Johanna, Davies, Rob, Remondino, Fabio, Caffo, Rossella (eds.). *Progress in Cultural Heritage Preservation. 4th International Conference, EuroMed 2012. Limassol, Cyprus, October/November 2012. Proceedings*, 404-413. Berlin: Springer.
- Skublewska-Paszkowska, Maria, Powroznik, Pawel, Smolka, Jakub, Milosz, Marek, Lukasik, Edyta, Mukhamedova, Dilbar, Milosz, Elzbieta. (2021). Methodology of 3D scanning of Intangible Cultural Heritage—The example of Lazgi dance. *Applied Sciences*, 11(23), 11586. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112311568>.
- Steyerl, Hito. (2015). *Factory of the Sun*. The Venice Biennale, Venice, Italy.
- Steyerl, Hito. (2016). A tank on a pedestal: Museums in an age of planetary civil war. *e-flux*, 70. Retrieved from <https://www.e-flux.com/journal/70/60543/a-tank-on-a-pedestal-museums-in-an-age-of-planetary-civil-war/>.
- Taylor, Diana. (2003). *The archive and the repertoire. Performing cultural memory in the Americas*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Vincent, Jordan Beth, Vincent Caitlin, Vincs, Kim, deLahunta, Scott, McCormick, John. (2018). Artworks-spawning-artworks: trans-disciplinary approaches to artistic spin-offs and evolution in the dance and digital context in Whatley, Sarah, Cisneros, Rosamaria K., Sabiescu, Amalia (eds.). *Digital Echoes: Spaces for Intangible and Performance-based Cultural Heritage* (pp. 283-299). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Waelde, Charlotte. (2018). Dance and law: From indifference to rapport in Whatley, Sarah, Cisneros,

Artículos

- Rosamaria K., Sabiescu, Amalia (eds.). *Digital Echoes: Spaces for Intangible and Performance-based Cultural Heritage* (pp. 321-336). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Waelde, Charlotte, Whatley, Sarah, Pavis, Mathilde. (2014). Let's dance! But who owns it?. *European Intellectual Property Review*, 36(4), 217-228. Retrieved from <http://www.sweetandmaxwell.co.uk/catalogue/productdetails.aspx?productid=7061&recordid=460>.
- Wallace, Benedikte, Martin, Charles P., Tørresen, Jim, Nymoene, Kristian. (2021). Learning embodied sound-motion mappings: Evaluating AI-generated dance improvisation. *C&C '21: Proceedings of the 13th Conference on Creativity and Cognition*, 1-9. New York: Association for Computing Machinery.
- Warren-Crow, Heather. (2017). Before and after *Ghostcatching*: Animation, primitivism, and the choreography of vitality. *Screen Bodies: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Experience, Perception, and Display*, 2(1), 22-44. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3167/screen.2017.020103>.
- Whitelaw, Mitchell. (2015). Generous interfaces for digital cultural collections. *Digital Humanities Quarterly*, 9(1). Retrieved from <https://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/9/1/000205/000205.html>.
- Zhou, Hao, Mudur, Sudhir P. (2006). On the use of 3D scanner for Chinese opera documentation in Zha, Hongbin, Pan, Zhigeng, Thwaites, Hal, Addison, Alonzo C., Forte, Maurizio (eds.). *Interactive Technologies and Sociotechnical Systems. 12th International Conference, VSMM 2006. Xi'an, China, October 2006. Proceedings*, 377-386. Berlin: Springer.

> Fecha de envío: **25/07/2023**

> Fecha de aceptación: **03/10/2023**

